

Sampling the Latent Space: Exploring the Creative Potential of Generative AI Through the Lens of Sample-Based Music Making

Ashley Noel-Hirst
Queen Mary University of London

Charalampos Saitis
Queen Mary University of London

Nick Bryan-Kinns
University of the Arts London

Abstract

Sample-based composition is a century-old practice in which artists repurpose existing sounds to create new music. As generative AI (GenAI) systems increasingly reuse existing material, they are often compared to sampling and remix practices. In this paper, we draw on the relatively mature tradition of sampling to address a key concern of GenAI: how might a tool which is dependent on the recycling of existing art support meaningful creativity? We present an ethnography and thematic analysis of a sample-based music community, connecting these insights to contemporary opportunities and challenges in GenAI design. We discuss how designers might support artists in engaging with environmental, fictional, communal, and agential dimensions of GenAI models and data, building on literature about sample-based music to speak not only to generative music but to GenAI systems more broadly.

1 Introduction

As generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) for music – training a model on existing sound data, manipulating it in some way, and creating novel output – has become more popular, it has attracted comparison to remix and sample-based practices where composers manipulate recorded sound to create new audio output. They appeal to a similar tension, the reuse of others' work on the one hand, and the creative agency of the artist on the other. In other words, they both raise questions of whether the process of making art from existing material can be considered meaningful. But, while the analogy of 'remix' has often been appealed to for the critique and design of GenAI systems, it has rarely been formulated on the basis of engaging remix-based and sample-based communities themselves. The research question (RQ) at the core of this paper is therefore: *What values and practices underpin sample-based music-making, and how might these guide the development of more meaningful generative AI tools?*

We undertake interviews and ethnography of two sample-based communities and reflect on how understanding creative practices in these communities might offer an alternative lens through which to view some of the challenges of using GenAI. Through thematic analysis we identify themes of sample-based practice (environment; reality; community; agency), before exploring how these themes relate to aspects of GenAI more broadly, such as data provenance, explainability and latent representations. In contributing this analysis and discussion, we attempt to support the creative and engineering communities in thinking about what we are really trying to do with our GenAI models, as well as who or what we are ascribing agency to in these systems.

2 Related work

2.1 Sample-based music

Sample-based composition – the process of composing new sounds from existing sounds – has evolved since the early-20th century. First, an electromechanical era (1920s-1970s) saw compositions for gramophones (Respighi, 1925; Schaeffer, 2012a), tape players (Seachrist, 2003), and other electromechanical assemblages (Teruggi, 2007). A digital era (1980s-2000s) consisted of hardware samplers such as the Akai MPC and SP-404, facilitating sampling in popular culture and the birth of hip-hop (Exarchos, 2019). Computational advances during this time enabled real-time manipulation of microscopic sound fragments through granular synthesis (Roads, 1988) and concatenative synthesis (Schwarz, 2007). An internet era (2000s onwards) transformed sample availability through online repositories (Fonseca et al., 2017), knowledge forums (Salavuo, 2006), and manipulation through networked performance environments (Makelberge, 2012).

Throughout these eras, a persistent tension has remained between the use of samples as either *sonic* or *intertextual* materials. Schaeffer (2012b) advocates the sonic : ‘as long as signification is predominant [...] we have literature and not music’ In this mode, sound is treated based on its qualities as a material, divorced from referential meaning. By contrast, the intertextual mode embraces cultural functions of sound, such as reference and quotation. Hip-hop producers, for example, use samples to negotiate issues of identity and cultural history (Watkins, 2005; Weheliye, 2005). Landy and Richards (2024) suggest that these are not two distinct schools of thought, but rather tensions that productively coexist in contemporary practice. Fisher (2013) suggests that acts and artefacts of the sonic mode might themselves be intertextual.

Some sample-based artists use AI tools to ‘crate dig in the latent space’ (Damien Roach, 2023), stream automatic remixes (Carr and Zukowski, 2024; Evans et al., 2024), and otherwise generate, organise or manipulate audio materials. Are we in a new ‘AI era’ of sampling and remix?

2.2 Generative AI in music

As computational power and data availability have increased in the past 5 years, generative music creation has shifted towards deep learning techniques, which produce more complex and realistic outputs based on audio training data. Civit et al. (2022) found that most GenAI music systems now use existing data, with 70% of generative models being deep learning-based. They also noted a rapidly growing interest in audio generative models that are either controlled by text input – for example, transformer-based architectures (Dhariwal et al., 2020; Borsos et al., 2023) and diffusion models (Huang et al., 2023a) – or that give users control through intermediate representations, such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) (Donahue et al., 2019; Dong et al., 2018) and auto-encoders (Tan and Herremans, 2020; Caillon and Esling, 2021a).

The increase of GenAI music audio systems trained on large datasets means corpora are more enormous, whilst at the same time we interact with smaller minutiae, and the fidelity of outputs are greatly increased. This in turn supports a range of music-making tasks with GenAI, such as in-painting (Garcia et al., 2023), style & timbre transfer (Bonnici et al., 2022; Cifka et al., 2021; Hung et al., 2019), embodied performance systems (Murray-Browne and Tigas, 2021), and intelligent music production (Deruty et al., 2022).

However, GenAI’s reliance on data attracts concern about the resultant *artwork itself* – ownership and authorship (Goetze, 2024); bias in data & features (Huang et al., 2023b) and non-diverse research communities (Civit et al., 2022) – as well as the music-making *process* and its meaningfulness (Kraaijeveld, 2024).

We are particularly interested in this *process* dimension. While psychology and human-computer interaction (HCI) literature highlights the importance of meaning-centred interaction design, (Diefenbach et al., 2014; Mekler and Hornbæk, 2019; Rosso et al., 2010), much existing HCI work on GenAI music systems focuses either on control (Bryan-Kinns et al., 2023) or human-adjacent interaction (Vear et al., 2023). Technoscientific approaches examine how the meaning of musical systems – including GenAI – is co-constructed within communities of practice through semiotic modes of communication (e.g., diagrams (Morrison, 2024), metaphorical language (Saitis et al., 2024, 2025)). Other, post-human and material accounts suggest new possibilities for what can make human-AI interaction uniquely meaningful, considering how artwork arises from complex networks of human

and non-human actors (Huang and Sturm, 2021; Armitage et al., 2023); or even that GenAI systems can themselves express creativity (Colton and Wiggins, 2012).

2.3 The metaphor of sampling in GenAI

The metaphor of ‘sampling’ and ‘remix’ in the design and artistic application of GenAI has become ubiquitous (Kato, 2024; Giuliani et al., 2023; Collins et al., 2020; Damien Roach, 2023).

The foundation of this metaphor is compelling: both samples and data appear to represent units of material that creators transform into new works. The analogy gains momentum from a growing attempt to ground data in something real: maybe sampling is the metaphor we need to draw out the materiality (Malafouris, 2013) and cultural situatedness (Haraway, 2013) of data.

Gunkel (2025) argues that while ‘remix has prepared us for the opportunities and challenges of [GenAI]’ it is important that we do not treat them as equivalent. GenAI does ‘not simply repeat or reproduce the artistic, moral, and legal challenges of remix’ but rather ‘recontextualises remix’ itself, introducing ‘an additional level of abstraction away from the source material’ that fundamentally changes its ontological status. They argue that GenAI should be analysed with respect to new social and economic dynamics new material constraints, and therefore a new unit of analysis.

There have been attempts to suggest such units. Born (2024) offers ‘*aggregate*’ to describe the decontextualisation of ‘data-ified sonic materials underlying generative AI’; here, the emphasis falls on abstraction and sanitisation, where samples are stripped of authorship and cultural situatedness necessary for intertextuality. Herndon (2023) offers ‘*spawning*’ — each AI instance is, for her, ‘spawning new instances of a person or thing’. This animates the AI, not as a tool, but as an agent with internal coherence. Privato and Magnusson (2024) reanimate sonic *hauntology* to foreground the spectral materiality and unstable aesthetics of AI-generated artefacts, extending Fisher’s (Fisher, 2013) notion of cultural ghosts to discuss the sonic materiality of generative outputs’ incoherence. Gioti et al. (2022) propose ‘*assemblage*’, adapted from Born (2005), to describe ML–human musical compositions as ‘distinctive manifestations of distributed creativity and collaboration between human and non-human actors’, emphasising the entangled, co-constitutive agency of systems, data, artists, and infrastructures.

3 Method

The study reported in this paper employs a two-part method of qualitative data collection and analysis. First, we engaged with a community of musicians who work with samples through a mixed-methods approach combining ethnographic observation and semi-structured interviews.

We conducted data collection across two events within London’s sample-based music community, CreateDefineRelease (CDR)¹, and ClubWIP², which are shown in Figure 1. While we did not prompt artists to use AI systems, occasional references emerged organically. Notably, AI tools were only minimally used by participants—possibly due to misalignment with their values or limited accessibility. This tension between traditional sampling practices and emerging GenAI tools forms a central focus of our inquiry.

CreateDefineRelease (CDR) A community interest company running since 2002 that nurtures independent music makers, particularly in Black electronic music. CDR sessions feature guest producers discussing their process in a club environment, bookended by “openCDR” segments where attendees’ tracks are played and discussed. The first author has been involved as both attendee and organizer for five years.

ClubWIP A creative challenge event where music makers compose pieces under specific limitations, often involving sample sources or transformation techniques. Tracks must be under one minute, and producers discuss their work with each other. These events have been operating since 2023 in partnership with local sound-systems.

¹<https://www.createdefinerelease.com/>

²<https://www.clubwip.co/>

(a) A CreateDefineRelease (CDR) event

(b) A Club WIP event

Figure 1: Our two observation sites: (a) CreateDefineRelease (CDR) (b) Club WIP.

3.1 Observations

The first author actively participated in these groups, attending 4 ClubWIPs (25-30 attendees per event) and 6 CDRs (60-80 attendees per event) over 12 months. Observations were recorded using a structured observation guide (Roller and Lavrakas, 2015) containing six key areas:

1. People (attendees)
2. Relations (connections between attendees)
3. Content (musical material)
4. Feeling (emotions expressed by participants or felt by observer)
5. Semiotic mode (techniques used to communicate content (Danielsson and Selander, 2021) - e.g. gestural)
6. Other (anything else of note)

3.2 Semi-structured interviews

While initial observational data was helpful for getting a sense of activities in the communities, in-depth, semi-structured interviews were used to draw out themes. The first author interviewed 7 artists (mean age 31.3, $SD=10.3$; mean experience 17.6 years, $SD=7.41$) who primarily use samples in their compositions. Participants had a range of musical practices, and most had engaged with AI either for interaction (e.g. gesture-to-sound mapping) or audio (e.g. neural audio synthesis) (Table 1, more detail in Appendix C).

Table 1: Participants’ musical practices and use of AI.

Participant		Use of AI	
ID	Practice	AI for Interaction	AI for Audio
P1	Ambient Musician, Pianist & Producer	-	-
P2	Performer, Instrument-Maker & Vocalist	✓	-
P3	Live-coding Performer	-	✓
P4	Interactive and Generative Music Composer	✓	✓
P5	Sound Designer	-	✓
P6	Composer for Television and Film	-	✓
P7	Percussionist and Hip-Hop Producer	-	-

Participants were recruited through CDR and ClubWIP, and selected based on their experience with sample-based music and their willingness to discuss their practice. Participants were compensated for

their time in line with musicians union teaching rates. This study was approved by the ethics board at the first author's institution.

The semi-structured format used thirteen questions (Appendix A), lasted 60-120 minutes and explored two main facets that had been identified in the ethnographic observations:

Material How artists perceive and communicate their source and output material

Methods How artists conceptualize and communicate sample transformation processes

Interviews were conducted in person, recorded, and transcribed. In addition to describing their music-making practice, artists provided a demonstration of their practice for analysis.

3.3 Data analysis

Data from the interviews were analysed using thematic analysis (TA) (Braun and Clarke, 2006) to identify key patterns and themes in sample-based music practices. Observation data was considered when relevant to themes. The first author followed the six steps of thematic analysis outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006): (i) transcription and familiarisation with the data; (ii) generating initial codes; (iii) searching for themes; (iv) reviewing themes; (v) defining and naming themes and sub-themes; and (vi) producing the report. The first author coded the data, completing stages (i-iv), then stages (iv-vi) were iterated upon, while the final author reviewed the codes and themes. The final themes were agreed upon and reported based on discussion between all authors.

4 Findings: sampling & creativity

We identified 113 unique codes (284, including repeats) through analysis of the interviews, which were then organized into four overarching themes: (i) Engaging with Environment (17 unique codes), (ii) Reality and Fiction (14), (iii) Community and Identity (12), and (iv) Negotiating Agencies (9). Sub-themes were developed by clustering related codes that reflected recurring ideas, practices, or tensions across participants' accounts. Table 2 presents an overview of the themes and sub-themes, along with their corresponding (non-unique) code counts. Sections 4.1 to 4.4 provide a summary of each theme, supported by illustrative quotes and descriptions of examples from our ethnographic observations.

4.1 Theme i: engaging with environment

Active Listening Artists reported not just looking for samples during defined periods, but rather being 'found by them' (P4) while going about daily life. More than composing, participants describe the act of sampling beginning first with deep, *active listening*, engaging with their environment (P5,6). 'You're just existing without thinking about making sounds, and then all of a sudden there's this sound [...] and [that's] when I record something.' (P1)

Collecting & Documenting Engagement with environment is taken further through the collection and documentation of sounds: '[I take] random sounds that I find interesting and then I resample them. It's like taking a picture of something. [I] don't always make something. I'm *recording* it, I mean it is what it is, the word says it all. It's a sample. It's a picture of sound.' (P1, *emphasis in original*); 'Sampling is just like capturing sound in the world however it's generated.' (P2)

Materiality Artists reported engaging with the tangible, material aspects of their environment, for example 'flowing water' (P2), but also treat sound itself as a material which is reflective not only of the environment (what it is sampling), but also of the technology used:

'Whether it's the zoom H6 or my iPhone, or that little zoom recorder that plugs into my phone, I have to work with different sounds [...] you know, the noise and the artefacts in there actually enhance what you're able to do with it [...] I think of sound is kind of like – if we're doing an artistic analogy – clay. And you're moulding it into whatever you need it to be.' (P5)

The relevance of a sounds materiality can be affected by its length, as P4 explains:

Table 2: Overview of themes and sub-themes identified in the thematic analysis. ‘Code Count’ reflects the total number of codes (including repeats) assigned to each sub-theme.

Theme	Sub-Themes	Code Count
Engaging with Environment	Active Listening	10
	Collecting and Documenting	6
	Digital Environment	5
	Materiality	3
	Sense of Place	2
Reality and Fiction	Design Fiction	8
	Verisimilitude	4
	Multimodal Expression	3
	Reality	3
Community and Identity	Reflection	10
	Competition	7
	Craft	6
	Communication	4
	Legal & Industry Pressures	1
Negotiating Agencies	Control	13
	Communicating Artist Role to Audiences	6
	Emergence	4

Figure 2: The relationship between sample length and cultural/material relevance – diagram from P1 (recreated for clarity)

‘Being able to take a very short fragment of sound [...] is much more material driven, there’s not context necessarily in that sample in the same way as the long-form samples [...] there isn’t this whole cultural context that surrounds it. It’s just a short piece of sound.’ (P4)

P1 also reflects this, explaining through a diagram (reproduced in Figure 2) that as a fragment of sound sampled gets smaller and smaller, its focus becomes more on its material and concrete reality, and less about its cultural relevance.

Figure 3: Arctype (Sam Scott) performs ‘ONLINECHORUS’ at Iklectik Art Lab – April 27th 2023. The piece resamples a live feed taken from social media website TikTok. Image courtesy of the artist.

Sense of Place Artists also described engaging with their environment in ways that relate to non-tangible, non-material aspects which are superimposed on one’s physical experience of an environment. The first of these aspects is in the relationship between artists’ identity and the place, such as nostalgia (‘Whenever I’m [home] in the mountains, I try to record things.’ - P1) or politics (‘I’ve also, like, done field recordings of protests and stuff like that’ - P1). P1 organises their sample library multimodally (sound and image) so as to better capture these non-sonic aspects of the sound.

Additionally, P1, P2, and P5 reflected on the *meaning* of a place, particularly the boundaries between human and natural environments. P2 questioned the concept of “nature,”: “I like playing with what “nature” means... Everything touched by humanity is augmented, which kind of further removes it from its “natural” state.” (P2). P1, meanwhile, focused on the impact of human activity on the environment, recalling an encounter with an industrial, human sound in an otherwise natural, non-human setting: “I was walking around and I heard this weird turbine making this ominous sound like that’s kinda strange. Like that was not supposed to be there, you know? Why did we make this?” (P1).

Digital Environment Digital and online spaces – such as the internet – are increasingly treated as distinct environments. Though lacking physical form, some artists described engaging with them through a sense of place (as discussed previously). Participant P4, for example, spoke about resampling ‘weird 500-view YouTube videos,’ describing these obscure corners of the internet as sonic niches they intentionally explore and reinterpret. Another participant from the CDR community (see Figure 3) treats their TikTok³ algorithm as a ‘personalised digital environment’ from which they sample.

4.2 Theme ii: reality and fiction

Reality Samples of environments were noted to bridge the gap between art and life. P1 suggests that they are able to relate their compositions to the real world by ‘having a collection of unconventional sound that [they] found in real life’. The act of sampling can also alter our relationship to reality. P3 described ‘audiation’, the process of ‘hearing the sound and its possible alternatives’ while also hearing the original sound for the first time.

Verisimilitude By situating real sounds within art, sampling presents an opportunity for artists to manipulate notions of truth. P2, who finds nature, the digital, and artificiality to be important narrative devices in their work, does this through the presence and absence of samples: ‘using field recordings and sound that references nature, I would create what I would call soundscapes [...] manipulating found sounds, creating something digitally that *feels* quite aesthetically natural’ (P2).

In contrast, AI resynthesis of recorded samples polarised artists on its truthfulness. In the ethnography a participant in ClubWIP had used an AI-driven, audio resynthesis tool (synplant⁴) to recreate a sample of another participant’s family member singing. The result was appreciated by the audience,

³[tiktok.com](https://www.tiktok.com)

⁴<https://soniccharge.com/synplant?IALWovUHJF=vVnSZmufe>

Figure 4: Distribution of semiotic modes (e.g., onomatopoeia, gesture, technical language) used in communication at Club WIP, highlighting variations in cross-group and within-group interaction.

but when they discovered the use of AI, they were polarised. Some decried it as cheating, and ‘no longer a sample anymore’ (ClubWIP attendee), while others found it innovative.

Design Fiction Other sample-based artists that we spoke to operate a broader definition of ‘sampling’ or ‘remix’. These tended to be more technologically driven artists. Of particular interest is the work of P2, who described the instruments they built as ‘an attempt to reconfigure relationships to sound’. In sampling, they are not only sampling the sound, but also the ideas and concepts behind interaction with the sound. This is a form of ‘design fiction’ where the artist is creating a new way of thinking through presenting new interactive prototypes.

Multimodality An important aspect of this interaction is *multimodality*. Many artists use standardised configurations for interacting multimodally with sound, for example, tactilly with sensors (P2), or visually via spectra (P4, 5, 6). However, artists also skew these configurations. For example: P6 describes ambisonic-gesture mappings as ‘getting inside a sound, tearing it apart, then replaying it’; P7 describes custom mappings for ‘performing samples as though they were a futuristic instrument’; and P4 uses interactive visuals to ‘play with the spatial and timbral associations of a sound’.

4.3 Theme iii: community and identity

‘My identity [is] in it because it’s the materials that I chose’ (P4)

‘If you give other people your code [and] sounds, they could just recreate your music’ (P3)

Craft A core aspect of the communities studied is their emphasis on craft. This manifests in shared activities and language. Many methods of socialising in the CDR community are built around the collecting of samples including crate digging (hunting for obscure vinyl), field recording, etc. The ClubWIP community is defined on the basis of sharing techniques. Group identity forms around shared techniques, creating subgroups with common reference points, for example, ‘yeah it’s got that incinerator sound’ (ClubWIP attendee discussing another attendee’s composition).

Communication At ClubWIP, conversations about sampling occurred both within established groups and between participants who had just met. This distinction shaped the *semiotic mode* used to communicate sampling processes (e.g., gesture, technical language, onomatopoeia). When describing their craft or asking questions, participants in cross-group conversations used less technical language and more onomatopoeia. In contrast, within-group communication featured more technical language and less onomatopoeia. These patterns are summarized in Figure 4.

Competition While there is a strong community drive, competition for work also shapes what elements of craft are shared, and who is accepted into which groups. Individual identity, virtuosity, and value are demonstrated by finding samples no-one else has, or manipulating commonplace samples in a way that no one else can.

‘As media composers, we need to have sonic elements in our scores that are not readily available to everybody else [...] So we are always looking for for new tools [...] to make our Sonic palettes as unique as possible’ (P5)

As a result of this link between sample-sourcing and individuality, people can be wary to disclose their samples, as it might be seen as sharing their ‘secret sauce’ (P7); dissolving their individuality (P1-7); or exposing them to financial/legal difficulty (P3,4).

Reflection Sampling often requires the repeated audition and manipulation of a sound. For example, P3 organises ideas in two dimensions: temporal (left to right) and conceptual (top to bottom). Commenting and un-commenting ideas in a live-coding program (P1) or arranging them in a grid-based DAW – such as Live’s ‘session mode’ (P1, 2, 4, 5 & 6)⁵ – allows for manipulation and repetition of the same sound or phrase. While this organisation is not exclusive to sampling, that sampling changes the context of an *existing* idea allows us to share and reflect on our ideas at an embryonic stage. P4 highlights how curating and reflecting on samples facilitates collaborative work:

‘One of my collaborators made like a dozen [samples], and then I came along and made a dozen more. [...] So the sound world gets collaboratively curated. “This is my interpretation of the prompt” or “this is my interpretation of the source sample”. [...] instead of meeting at the compositional stage where you perhaps interject some of your meaning, you’ve already got some there because it’s in the way that the materials were curated.’

Legal & Industry Pressures External factors such as AI sample-detection, music informatic retrieval (MIR) technology and their use for copyright enforcement have shaped the formation of communities in giving them something to resist.

‘I’m not trying to get sued, so I have to think very carefully about what I use now.’ (P7)

Artists reported going increasingly far to evade detection. They are careful to obfuscate, deconstruct or re-fabricate material ‘until it legally becomes a separate entity’ (P3), while keeping enough of the sample present to signal its use to those in the know. For example, P3 and P4 reported using style transfer⁶ and other generative AI techniques as a route around the legal issues of sampling. In creating new permutations of existing samples, they are able to retain interesting aspects of the original sound while avoiding copyright issues. Additionally, they increase their palette of sounds, which helps with creative sound design tasks

Another external factor in the community is the use of GenAI for music creation by the wider music industry. This has applied pressure to professionals, particularly those in business to business domains, such as sound design for moving image:

‘As sound designers, we’re competing against AI [that has the ability to] generate sounds on its own. So [...] we have to keep in mind how our sounds are going to still sound unique, but also sound high enough quality than AI can’t do the same thing’ (P5)

4.4 Theme iv: negotiating agencies

‘[Playing piano] there’s a bit of agency [but when recording] the sample, I can’t really mess with this sound that I’m given. [...] I don’t have as much control.’ (P1)

Emergence In the process of manipulating a sample, artists describe a process of gradually understanding and working with initially unfamiliar sounds and materials, moving from divergent, chaotic interaction with their environment toward creative emergence, and eventually, a more curatorial convergence. P2, an artist who designs their own sample-based instruments, described the process

⁵Live is a digital audio workstation (DAW), produced by Ableton <https://www.ableton.com/live/>

⁶For example, via ‘remix’ and ‘extend’ modes on popular audio text-prompting tools Suno <https://www.suno.ai> and Udio <https://www.udio.com>

of creating embodied digital environments: ‘Putting samples in a space, leaving a lot of that to the algorithm [...] using my body to trigger them and seeing what happens’. They placed a great deal of importance on the agency of the algorithm, the surprise of the content of the sample, and their own ability to navigate and reflect on this space through embodied action and listening. P4 highlights the importance of the emergent properties of a sample-based system, and how this can be a source of inspiration:

‘How probable is it that you would come up with a synth patch that does exactly what this thing does? [...] how probable is it you would have been able to make this through sampling? I think sampling makes this particular sound easy to make.’

Control Lack of control is for many a source of creative inspiration. Samples can serve as creative partners, shaping the outcome of a piece as much as the artist. ‘The materials do influence what you do with them’ (P4). Some welcome this lack of control:

‘I’m really relinquishing control in my practise, because like I don’t like doing that in my day-to-day life. And it feels quite liberating.’ (P2)

But, others find it important to limit their use of samples so as to maximise their own control & responsibility:

‘Limited source material means I have to do more work, which means I have more ownership over my final outcome.’ (P3)

Communicating Artist Role to Audiences Disentangling agency becomes more important when considering performing or replaying sample-based music. It is important to artists to have some level of control over the outcome of a piece, and that they can communicate what they are doing to audiences during live performance. For example, P2 emphasised embodiment in performing sample-manipulation while P3 highlighted the live-coding motto ‘show us your screens’:

‘A big part of the practise as well is about this kind of interaction with the audience or sharing the screen so the audience can see the code being changed and executed in real-time [...] its designed to be easily parsed by people because it uses natural language.’ (P3)

This, in turn, shapes the language used to label and describe samples. P3’s live-coding sample library must be descriptive (for audiences) yet concise (for the performer). The result is onomatopoeic and semantic descriptions of the sounds (e.g. ‘big_swoosh’).

5 Discussion

Sampling doesn’t simply make music-making easier. In fact, there are many reasons to be discouraged from sampling, such as legal pressures, or the effort and equipment required to find original samples. Our ethnographic work suggests that the value in sampling is as a meaning-making process which engages artists with their environment (4.1); explores boundaries of reality and fiction (4.2); forms and reflects community (4.3); and foregrounds agential relationships (4.4).

Here, we consider existing literature alongside the themes which arose in our ethnography, reflecting on sample-based values and highlighting opportunities and challenges to musical GenAI.

5.1 Theme i: engaging with environment

In collecting, manipulating, and recontextualizing sounds, sample-based artists become sensitized to relationships within their environment. We might consider how GenAI foregrounds its socio-materiality.

Challenge: Data provenance and modality Sections (4.3,4.3), and existing literature (Blackburn, 2019) suggest that a sound’s appeal often extends far beyond its sonic properties to information *about* it, often multimodally. A challenge for current GenAI interfaces is transparent provenance throughout the entire data lifecycle (data collection, model architecture, training, representation, and output). Allowing users to relate these aspects to the data itself might support users in deeper,

explicitly socio-material relationships with data, understanding and trusting the resultant model more fully as a result.

Opportunity: Latent spaces as socio-material environments Samples are increasingly found and created in digital environments, highlighting the potential of non-tangible spaces for socio-material exploration. There is opportunity to expand this metaphor: intermediate representations in GenAIs – such as those used in GANs and auto-encoders – could be reconceptualized as environments to be explored through existing sound practices like deep listening and soundwalking. This might expand our understanding of GenAI’s digital materiality, supporting critical engagement with embedded values and contexts.

5.2 Theme ii: reality and fiction

Many sample-based artists place great importance on truth (that a sample references a distinct event or thing). By contrast, an AI generated/manipulated sound might often be said to have ‘verisimilitude’ (the appearance of truth rather than ‘truth’ itself). New textual meaning in GenAI sampling might be found by deliberately foregrounding this tension between reality and fiction.

Challenge: Explaining reality We might broaden explainability frameworks in audio GenAI to help users understand not just how sounds are transformed technically but how meaning might be preserved or altered. This might help artists better understand what aspects of multiple original recordings remain ‘true’ in an AI-manipulated/aggregated result.

Opportunity: Embracing fiction Conversely, AI outputs’ detachment from reality presents creative opportunities, inviting musicians to explore new sonic territories with their own internal logic. Rather than pursuing verisimilitude, we could design AI audio tools that deliberately explore ‘impossible’ sounds and alternate sonic realities, treating latent spaces as creative environments rather than imperfect mirrors of reality. If AI is not able to reproduce sounds exactly, then why try to produce anything like them?

5.3 Theme iii: community and identity

We described sample-based composition as a highly situated practice: meaning is co-produced within communities of practice, and modes of representing, communicating and interacting with data are often tied to these particular communities.

Challenge: What is an AI’s perspective? Communities of practice are made up of individuals with different strengths, weaknesses, and disciplinary perspectives. This plurality brings dynamism and diversity, which is integral to a craft-based community. In contrast, many GenAI systems are designed to appear omnivalent and all-knowing – lacking clear perspective or positionality. A clear challenge, then is presenting AI with a defined perspective – through elements such as belief, language, or perception. Additionally, Vear et al. (2023) suggest that such systems that are more likely to be trusted and understood by artists.

Opportunity: Rethinking Modality and Explainability in AI

GenAI’s knowledge need not be funnelled through limited and universal representations such as language. Personalisation, craft, and exploration were a core aspect of the formation of individual identity for many of our sample-based participants, and modes of communication correlated to the formation of communities (see Figure 4). Exemplified by approaches such as network bending (Broad et al., 2021; Yee-King and McCallum, 2021), the inner workings of generative AI systems may present fertile ground for artistic exploration if we embrace more flexible architectural approaches, moving beyond static notions of interpretability or evaluation, and toward more fluid, contextual representations that embrace vague semantics and adapt to community-specific interaction modes (such as gesture, sonic material or community keywords).

5.4 Theme iv: negotiating agencies

Having explored the complex interplay between human creators and sample-based systems, we think it is important to consider key tensions between emergence, control, and communication to audiences when designing GenAI systems.

Figure 5: A speculative diagram (not based on data). We extrapolate from our observations on sample-length and intertextuality to highlight a gap in current AI tools, considering GenAI alongside established sampling technologies and their intertextual and sonic capacities

Challenge: Explanations for Audiences Explainability matters differently for different people in the system. While artists experience their agency directly through practice, audiences struggle to understand these complex technological assemblages. While agentially complex and emergent approaches are may be preferred over traditional explainability within arts practice, recognizing and communicating the agential qualities of data itself is important for audiences. Explainability might therefore be explored as a multi-faceted quality, containing both artist-oriented and audience-oriented aspects. The challenge is in designing for both facets at once.

Opportunity: Balancing control vs emergence What is the role of the human in a creative process that reuses existing data? What other agents are a artists interacting with when they use a GenAI system? Rather than simply maximizing user control, artistic practice with GenAI requires acknowledging multiple agencies at play – in data collection, curation, and operationalization. Similar to how sample-based communities work with sound with varying degrees of control, we can design systems that allow (or even require) artists to balance their own control against emergent qualities of the system, leading to precise manipulation and productive uncertainty.

5.5 Sampling the latent space

Is GenAI a remix technology? When a ClubWIP participant used a re-synthesis tool (Synplant) to manipulate a sample, they unknowingly stepped into a debate about the ontology of data: does AI-resynthesized media retain its original referent?

It is reasonable to suggest that GenAI can support remix, particularly through new forms of sonic manipulation. However, like a distortion pedal used in remixing but not a remix tool itself, GenAI is not inherently a remix technology. Our ethnographic work suggests that sampling often gains meaning from real-world reference and community context – dimensions flattened when AI disrupts provenance and aggregates cultural perspectives.

We revisit Figure 2, where shorter samples emphasize sonic qualities and longer ones foreground intertextual qualities. Extending this with Figure 5, we ask: can GenAI address both?

Most current systems lean heavily into sonic novelty while lacking capacity for cultural reference. Nonetheless, we see emerging possibilities. Concepts like ‘assemblage’ and ‘spawn’ suggest AI-native units of socio-technical production and analysis. We propose a shift toward these approaches – a form of *meta-textual* sampling in which meaning is derived not from external cultural references, but from the generative process, dataset, or internal dynamics of the system itself. If GenAI can support this kind of referentiality, it may enable new modes of meaning aligned with the themes explored throughout this paper.

5.6 Closing remarks

This paper examined creativity and meaning in a sample-based music community, highlighting themes of environment, fiction, community, and agency. We critique how GenAI tools intersect with these, often flattening cultural context. We propose that researchers and developers explore how GenAI might better support intertextuality, whether through clearer provenance or by engaging AI systems as generative, referential materials in their own right.

Ethics Statement

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee at the lead author’s institution.

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⁷<https://soundlikethese.com/>

⁸<https://soundscape11c.com/>

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A Interview Questions

Each interview began (Question 1, 2) by asking the artist(s) to provide an overview of their practice and (3) to describe the process of making a piece in practical detail. Then (4–6), they were asked about their relationship to the material they are sampling. With the next set of questions (7–10), they were asked questions about their model of the processes they use. Finally (11–13), they were invited to reflect on the impact of technologies and AI on these aspects of the practice.

[Notes to the interviewer are in square brackets]

1. Please introduce yourself and describe your practice
2. Describe the last piece that you made or something that you are working on at the moment. And the role sampling plays in that. . .
3. Describe your process of making an composition or performance.
4. How would you describe a sample to a non-musician?
5. Where do you usually get samples from? [follow up on locations, habits, intentions]
6. What are key things which makes something a 'good/bad' sample? [Be intentionally vague about aesthetic and non-aesthetic components here, allow them to outline their own hierarchy without pushing too much]
7. [follow up] When evaluating a piece of music, some musicians might think of qualities like 'time', or 'pitch'. How relevant are these to you? If not, are there any other qualities which you think are worth considering about a sample?
8. Once you have identified that there is a sample you'd like to use/manipulate, what are some ways you might proceed?
9. Can you pick one of those processes and explain it to a non-musician? You can use words or a sketch to describe this.
10. [follow up](How much) does control matter in this process?
11. Discuss 'technology' in the context of sampling?
12. Has your process, or understanding of sampling processes changed at any point? Can you talk me through a time where this has happened or what has brought it on?
13. Do you use artificial intelligence technologies in your work/ process? If so, what for? If not, why not? [hopefully they will talk about samples, here, but if they don't that's also fine]

B Audio Examples – Club WIP

Club WIP maintains an archive of all past events, which includes the source sound for each challenge, as well as participant responses. These can be found here: <https://www.clubwip.co/past-events>

C AI Use by Participants

This paper is not primarily concerned with how sample-based musicians are using AI. However, we did observe some AI use, that we felt was useful to share. This section outlines all AI systems used by participants.

C.1 Interviewees

P2 used AI to create mappings between sensors/instruments they had built and external sampler systems. They employed a mixture of their own software created in MaxMSP, as well as Wekinator (Fiebrink and Cook, 2010) to map gestures. P3 used AI to create original samples (Riffusion⁹, Suno¹⁰), and timbre transfer tools (Caillon and Esling, 2021b) to manipulate them. They also used custom-made AI to manipulate MIDI sequences.

P4 used existing AI tools to create instrument mappings in MaxMSP (FluCoMa (Tremblay et al., 2021), MuBu (Schnell et al., 2009)), as well as for audio manipulation and generation (RAVE (Caillon and Esling, 2021b), MuBu (Schnell et al., 2009)). They also used a plethora of custom-built models: wavelets and Joint Time-Frequency Scattering (JTFS) for timbre manipulation and spatial mapping; and k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) classification for audio-based interaction.

⁹<https://www.riffusion.com/>

¹⁰<https://suno.com/>

P5 described using AI to generate samples that were later manipulated in a DAW. They also used AI for sample organization, for example via descriptor space dimension reduction such as XO by XLN Audio¹¹. A key element of their practice involved source separation (Hennequin et al., 2020) and pitch control (Melodyne¹²), though they seemed to not regard these as "the same type of AI."

P6 used AI for MIDI data manipulation on the web (MidiMe¹³).

C.2 Ethnography Participants

During fieldwork, the first author observed relatively few instances of AI use by participants. The vast majority (>10) of instances were for stem separation (Spleeter, Lalal.ai¹⁴, Serato Stems¹⁵). Some participants (5) used AI to generate samples (Suno, Riffusion, MusicLM¹⁶, TwoShot¹⁷). Very few (3) participants used AI to manipulate samples beyond typical pitch and source separation, and all of these cases involved sound matching or resynthesis (e.g., Synplant¹⁸).

¹¹<https://www.xlnaudio.com/products/xo>

¹²<https://www.celemony.com/en/melodyne/what-is-melodyne>

¹³<https://midi-me.glitch.me/>

¹⁴<https://www.lalal.ai>

¹⁵<https://serato.com/dj/pro/stems>

¹⁶<https://musiclm.com/>

¹⁷<https://twoshot.app/>

¹⁸<https://soniccharge.com/synplant>